

Comparison of crop stress and soil maps to enhance variable rate irrigation prescriptions

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Abstract

Soil textural variability within many irrigated fields diminishes the effectiveness of conventional irrigation management, and scheduling methods that assume uniform soil conditions may produce less than satisfactory results. Furthermore, benefits of variable-rate application of agrochemicals, seeds, and nutrients can be partially masked by applying inappropriate amounts of water. Center pivot irrigation systems can be equipped with variable rate irrigation (VRI) capability and commercial VRI systems have been shown to perform dependably. Soil properties will impact the optimal application rate for a given location, but that information will need to be supplemented with measures of crop stress for in-season adjustment. A field study was conducted at the University of Missouri Fisher Delta Research Center Marsh Farm at Portageville in 2016 with the objective to compare soil and in-season stress maps to help determine their relationship. Apparent soil electrical conductivity (ECa) data were used to estimate the clay content and infrared thermometers (IRT) were suspended from the center pivot system to measure canopy temperature. While much of the growing season had adequate rainfall that prevented high water deficit stress levels, measurements on 5 July demonstrated spatial variability in canopy temperature and an integrated crop water stress index (iCWSI) that appeared to be correlated with soil texture. While seed cotton yield incorporated more than just the factors discussed in this report, areas of lowest clay content corresponded with the lowest yields. Additional data will be collected under a range of conditions and used for statistical comparisons of the observed effects.

Background

Soil textural variability within many irrigated fields diminishes the effectiveness of conventional irrigation management with respect to irrigation uniformity, scheduling, and water use efficiency. Irrigation scheduling methods that assume uniform soil conditions may produce less than satisfactory results on highly variable soils, contributing to a lack of commitment to irrigation scheduling by producers even though, in general, scheduling improves overall crop production. While soil sampling and testing a dense grid of locations within a field would be expensive and time consuming, mobile measurements of apparent soil electrical conductivity (ECa) have become widely used to map soil variability because ECa responds to a number of important soil physical and chemical properties, and mobile measurements are relatively quick and inexpensive. In non-saline soils, most of the variation in ECa is a function of soil texture, moisture content, bulk density, and cation exchange capacity (CEC) (Corwin & Lesch, 2005). If two or more ECa measurements with different depth response functions are available, mathematical inversion can be used to calibrate layer EC values to layer soil properties (Monteiro Santos, et al., 2010). Many mobile instruments provide the required multiple readings simultaneously while traversing a field.

Benefits of variable-rate application of agrochemicals, seeds, and nutrients can be partially masked by applying inappropriate amounts of water. However, center pivot irrigation systems can be equipped with variable rate irrigation (VRI) capability for site specific water application, and commercial VRI systems have been tested and shown to perform dependably (O'Shaughnessy, et al., 2013; Sui & Fisher, 2015). This logical complement to variable rate application of other inputs has producers seeking guidance for preparing prescriptions for optimal water application. Soil properties will impact

the optimal application rate for a given location, but that information will need to be supplemented with measures of crop stress for in-season adjustment. In the U.S., the Bushland, Texas, research team with the U.S. Department of Agriculture's Agricultural Research Service (ARS) recently patented an Irrigation Scheduling Supervisory Control And Data Acquisition (ISSCADA) system (Evelt, et al 2014) that can control VRI systems. With integrated sensor network subsystems, the ISSCADA system detects variable crop water needs and provides spatially variable recommendations for watering rates.

While a crop water stress index (CWSI) has been used to schedule irrigations in many regions, a method of integrating the CWSI over a day resulting in a CWSI and time threshold (CWSI-TT) or integrated CWSI (iCWSI) was presented by (O'Shaughnessy, et al., 2012) as a way to reduce some of the limitations of the traditional CWSI measurements. In the ISSCADA system, infrared thermometer (IRT) sensors are installed to view the crop at oblique angles and thus can report accurate canopy temperature data under less than full cover. However, it is uncertain how ISSCADA systems that rely on plant feedback will perform under extended periods of cloud cover and in climates with high humidity. The overall goal of this research is to test in a more humid climate an ISSCADA system developed and tested under generally arid conditions. The specific objective of the work reported here was to compare soil and in-season stress maps to help determine their relationship.

Methods

A field study was conducted at the University of Missouri Fisher Delta Research Center Marsh Farm at Portageville (36.41° N, 89.70° W) during the 2016 growing season to investigate irrigated cotton production. The rectangular field is approximately 5 ha, 320 m by 156 m, with the primary slope in the south to north (320 m) direction. It is located roughly 14 km west of the Mississippi River and lies within the New Madrid Seismic Zone. The combination of alluvial, eolian, and seismic activity over the years has resulted in highly variable soils in the region. While farming activities, including precision land grading, have made the effects less obvious, they still exist. The test location had been in corn production for three years prior to establishing this experiment. Daily and hourly weather data were collected approximately 600 m from the most distant part of the study site and placed on the University of Missouri Agricultural Electronic Bulletin Board (AgEBB; <http://agebb.missouri.edu/>).

Soil mapping units within the study field included Tiptonville silt loam (fine-silty, mixed, superactive, thermic Oxyaquic Argiudolls), which made up the majority of the field, and Reelfoot loam and sandy loam (fine-silty, mixed, superactive, thermic Aquic Argiudolls) (USDA-SCS, 1971) (Fig. 1). However, the field contains areas of high sand content that are too small to show up in the soils map. To provide higher resolution information, mobile ECa data were collected on 13 April 2016. A Veris MSP3 system (Veris Technologies, Inc., Salina, KS, USA) was used to collect data on a 1-s interval and a 10-m transect spacing. The MSP3 system includes optical and pH sensing; however, only the ECa data were used in this study. Soil texture data (sand, silt, and clay fractions) from laboratory analysis were obtained by soil horizon from 8 calibration locations within the study field and an adjoining 5 ha field. These locations were chosen to cover the range in mobile ECa data values obtained. Veris ECa data were inverted using the invVERIS software package (EMTOMO, Odivelas, Portugal) and layer EC values at the calibration locations were related to measured soil properties using linear regression. A detailed description of the procedure, including validation of the findings, was reported by Sudduth et al. (2017).

Figure 1. Aerial image of study field showing soil mapping units and estimated clay content in top 0.1-m layer. Groupings represent quintiles of the measured data points.

The field was bedded in the north-south direction with a row spacing of 0.97 m and the cotton variety PHY 333WRF was seeded at 13 seed m⁻¹ on 23 May. Nitrogen (134 kg N ha⁻¹) was broadcast applied at approximately the first square growth stage. Reduced tillage was utilized and standard cultural practices for weed and insect control for producing irrigated cotton in Missouri were employed. Growth regulator, insecticide, and defoliant were applied as blanket treatments to the whole field. The crop was harvested on 10 November with a Case IH 2155 cotton spindle picker (Case IH, Racine, WI, USA) equipped with an Ag Leader Insight (Ag Leader Technology, Ames, IA, USA) yield monitor system with sensors for every row. The yield monitor was calibrated by placing the cotton from each load in a boll buggy equipped with scales (Short Line Manufacturing, Shaw, MS, USA).

The study field and adjoining field were irrigated using a 160 m Valley 6000 center pivot irrigation system (Valmont Irrigation, Valley, NE, USA) with a Valley Zone Control VRI system. The system included seven independently controlled zones of approximately equal area, except for the outermost zone, which consisted of the three sprinklers on the 5-m overhang beyond the outer drive tower. Six Dynamax SapIP-IRT sensors (Dynamax, Inc., Houston, TX, USA) were mounted to the pivot lateral and two were placed at stationary locations within the field. The IRTs were included in a wireless network with a remote computer where the data were collected and stored. The observed canopy temperatures, together with the locally observed weather data, were used to calculate iCWSI values for the irrigation management zones.

Results and discussion

The clay content in the top 0.1-m soil layer fit very well with the measured validation data and the inversion estimate (Sudduth, et al., 2017). Clay content had a better fit than sand and those data were included in Figure 1. While roughly three fourths of the field was in the same mapping unit (Tiptonville silt loam), the estimated clay content revealed much more variability. Areas of very small clay content, and therefore large sand content, made up a large portion of the field, with more than 40% of the points containing less than 10% clay.

Figure 2 shows the daily maximum and minimum temperatures, together with the cumulative rainfall and estimated short grass reference evapotranspiration (ET_o) measured from the nearby weather station from planting through the end of September. Air temperatures were typical for the region with fairly wide fluctuations, even during the summer. Rainfall was plentiful during much of the growing season, with 109 mm between planting and 16 June. Only an additional 24 mm was observed in the following 38 days, but then 247 mm of rainfall was recorded between 24 July and 26 August. Although little rainfall was observed from 26 August through the end of September, University of Missouri guidelines do not recommend cotton irrigation after mid-August.

Figure 2. Daily maximum and minimum temperature, together with cumulative rainfall and estimated ET_o from planting through the end of September.

Canopy temperature data for the field were obtained by rotating the center pivot without irrigating, resulting in an IRT scan of the field. Figure 3 shows the canopy temperature in each VRI management zone based on an IRT scan on 5 July, which was during the driest portion of the growing season (Fig. 2) and before any irrigation applications. Temperatures ranging from 36 to 49°C were observed. Although no statistical comparisons have been conducted as of this writing, greater temperatures appear to coincide with smaller clay contents. The iCWSI values mirrored the canopy temperatures with very few minor exceptions (Fig. 4). The areas with the greatest stress were visually correlated with the lowest clay content, although data from additional dates and statistical comparisons will be required to determine the actual relationship.

Figure 3. Canopy temperature in each of the seven VRI management zones based on an IRT scan on 5 July. Groupings are equal intervals of the temperature range. Black lines represent the outer boundaries of the VRI management zones.

Figure 4. Integrated crop water stress index (iCWSI) in each of the seven VRI management zones based on an IRT scan and weather on 5 July. Groupings are equal intervals of the index range. Black lines represent the outer boundaries of the VRI management zones.

Finally, crop yield incorporates all of the stresses encountered over the course of the growing season (Fig. 5). Irrigation treatment effects that were not discussed in this report were confounded with the other factors. However, with the amount of rainfall received during the season (Fig. 2), water deficit stresses would not be expected to be great. With the high density of yield data points (every row by every second), the patterns in the data stand out more vividly, with the red areas of lowest yield (Fig. 5) corresponding with the red areas of lowest clay content (Fig. 1). There is some apparent correlation between iCWSI (Fig. 4) and yield as well. Similarly, Shaughnessy et al. (2011) demonstrated a significant strong correlation ($r^2 = 0.78$) between seasonally integrated CWSI and cotton yield in the drier of two years of study, but not for the wetter year that featured heavy rainfall in mid-August.

Conclusion

This study addressed the relationship between crop water stress and soil characteristics in cotton production. While a more extensive dataset and statistical comparisons will be needed to understand the connections, some qualitative observations were clear:

As seen in other studies, soil mapping units do not have enough spatial resolution and precision for directing site-specific applications in most cases.

- While much of the growing season had adequate rainfall to prevent high water deficit stress levels, measurements on 5 July demonstrated spatial variability in canopy temperature and iCWSI that appeared to be correlated with soil texture.
- While seed cotton yield incorporated more than just the factors discussed in this report, areas of lowest clay content corresponded with the lowest yields.

Figure 5. Seed cotton yield. Groupings represent quintiles of the measured data points.

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Mention of trade names or commercial products in this paper is solely for the purpose of providing specific information and does not imply recommendation or endorsement by the United States Department of Agriculture.

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